

PROACTIVE LEGAL SOLUTIONS FOR THE DIGITAL CLASSROOM: PROTECTING THE RIGHTS AND HEALTH OF ONLINE EDUCATORS IN GEORGIA

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Abstract

As online education becomes increasingly prevalent, the need for proactive legal frameworks to safeguard the rights and well-being of online educators has never been more pressing. The article explores the application of Proactive Law in addressing the unique challenges faced by online educators in Georgia. Proactive Law, with its emphasis on prevention, foresight, and interdisciplinary collaboration, offers a novel approach to mitigating the health and legal risks associated with digital teaching environments. We begin by identifying the primary health and safety risks encountered by online educators, including ergonomic injuries, mental health concerns, and the challenges of maintaining professional boundaries in a digital space. Additionally, we examine the legal uncertainties surrounding intellectual property rights, data privacy, and the adequacy of current contracts and institutional policies in protecting educators' interests, with a focus on the "Law of Georgia on Health Care" and the "Organic Law of Georgia on Occupational Health and Safety." The article then introduces Proactive Law as a framework that can be modified to enhance the protection of online educators. We propose specific legal measures, such as ergonomic regulations, mental health support requirements, and proactive contract design, to address these issues. Comparative insights from international practices are also discussed to provide a broader context and identify potential models for Georgia. Furthermore, we analyze the current legal landscape in Georgia and propose reforms to incorporate proactive legal strategies into existing frameworks. By emphasizing the need for proactive measures, the article aims to foster a more resilient, equitable, and human-centric legal environment for online educators. In conclusion, we call for policymakers and educational institutions in Georgia to adopt these proactive legal solutions to ensure the health and rights of online educators are adequately protected. The article highlights the importance of continuous research and policy adaptation as online education continues to evolve.

Keywords: Proactive Law, Online Educators' Rights, Health and Safety, Georgia.

I. Introduction:

The Importance of Online Education

Online education has emerged as a critical component of the modern educational landscape, offering flexibility and accessibility to learners across the globe. The COVID-19 pandemic has accelerated this shift, emphasizing the need for robust online learning systems. In Georgia, this transition has been particularly significant, revealing both opportunities and challenges in adapting to digital education (Bidzinaishvili, 2021). The rise of online education has prompted a reevaluation of educational methodologies and legal frameworks, highlighting the importance of addressing the needs and rights of online educators.

Georgia's Response to Online Education

In response to the surge in online learning, Georgia has undertaken initiatives to enhance its educational infrastructure. The government has adapted policies to support online education, as evidenced by the *Distance Learning Management for Practical School Administrators* guide (2021). However, this guide lacks coverage of educators' rights and well-being, an area this article aims to address.

In May 2020, Ilia State University hosted discussions on distance learning, exploring international experiences and support mechanisms for both students and educators (Ilia State University, 2020). Additionally, the *National Center for Educational Quality Enhancement* (NCEQE), in collaboration with EWMI and USAID, developed guidelines for online and blended learning quality assessment (Crozier & Greer, 2020).

Although these guidelines focus on maintaining educational quality, they do not adequately address the legal and health protections for educators, highlighting the need for future reforms.

Yasmine Mitaishvili-Rayyis documents ongoing educational reforms but emphasizes the need for comprehensive policy adjustments to address educator rights (Mitaishvili-Rayyis, 2023). Despite active exploration of online education challenges by the Georgian scientific community, there is limited evidence that administrators prioritize the protection of online educators' rights and well-being. This gap underscores the necessity for a more comprehensive approach that includes educator protections alongside educational reforms.

The NCEQE document provides valuable insights into maintaining educational quality but overlooks educators' legal protections. This supports the broader argument for legislative frameworks that not only enhance educational content and infrastructure but also safeguard the rights and well-being of online educators in Georgia's evolving educational landscape.

Post-Pandemic Developments and Challenges Faced

The transition to online education in Georgia, accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic, exposed significant gaps in digital infrastructure and pedagogical approaches. Bakakuri's 2020 report highlights that Georgian higher education institutions (HEIs) made notable progress in adapting to online teaching, yet challenges

with digital infrastructure and practical education components persisted (Bakakuri, 2020; Kadagidze, 2024). Additionally, an audit supported by USAID revealed substantial disparities in access to technology and resources affecting both students and educators (State Audit Office of Georgia, 2022).

International efforts, such as the integration of the Estonian educational model into Georgian schools, have aimed to modernize education with digital tools and innovative methods (Gvazava, 2019). However, these initiatives have not explicitly addressed the legal and health protections needed for online educators.

Challenges remain, as Bidzinaishvili (2021) identifies ongoing issues with online education quality and educator qualifications. Ergeshidze (2020) further underscores public concerns regarding access and educational quality, reflecting broader systemic issues impacting educators and students.

Sirotoová et al. (2023) report that while distance education provides flexibility and accessibility, it also presents significant challenges such as diminished physical contact and reduced student motivation. These insights underscore the necessity for proactive legal frameworks to safeguard educators' rights and well-being. Despite recent legislative amendments aimed at addressing online education challenges, these changes often focus more on educational content and infrastructure rather than the specific needs of online educators. There remains a substantial gap in legal protections for educators working in digital environments.

II. Legislative Framework for Distance Learning and Its Implications for Online Educators:

Recent Developments in Distance Learning Regulations in Georgia

On September 2, 2024, the Georgian Ministry of Education, Science, and Youth approved new regulations for distance learning in vocational education. These regulations define synchronous and asynchronous formats and permit remote delivery and assessment of vocational program components (Ministry of Education, Science, and Youth of Georgia, 2024). While this regulatory shift advances vocational training through distance education, it does not address educators' legal protections.

On March 11, 2024, a legislative package was introduced to reform distance learning, including partial electronic learning and the creation of "online universities." The Ministry of Education is tasked with developing standards for these institutions (edu.aris.ge., 2024). This reform aims to enhance access and standardize online education but does not explicitly address educator protections.

On August 30, 2024, Order No. 142/n set regulations for electronic learning in higher education, defining eligible academic fields and credit limits (Georgian Legislative Herald, 2024). This order clarifies the scope of electronic education, affecting institutional integration and student engagement.

The 2024 State Budget Law outlines changes in general education, including adjustments to personnel compensation and funding models (etaloni.ge., 2023). These adjustments are intended to align salaries with

educational reforms and distance learning methodologies.

The *Law of Georgia on Health Care* addresses general health protection but lacks specific provisions for educators' health rights (Georgian Legislative Herald, 2023, November 30). Similarly, the *Organic Law of Georgia on Occupational Health and Safety* sets standards for traditional workplaces but does not cover online work environments (Georgian Legislative Herald, 2023, May 31).

The evolving legislative framework for distance and online education highlights a shift towards digital learning integration. However, specific legal protections for online educators remain insufficient. Understanding these legislative changes is crucial for advocating comprehensive protections for educators in the digital classroom.

III. Proactive Law: A Framework for Protecting Educators' Rights

By anticipating potential challenges and implementing preventive measures, Proactive Law aims to create a more resilient and equitable legal environment. Thus, in the context of online education, Proactive Law can be instrumental in safeguarding educators' rights and well-being. For example, internationally, Proactive Law has been applied in various sectors to mitigate risks. For instance, in the Netherlands, proactive legal frameworks in the workplace include robust regulations for ergonomic standards and mental health support, which are extended to online work environments (Bakker & Demerouti, 2017). These frameworks could serve as a model for Georgia, highlighting the benefits of preventive legal strategies in protecting educators.

Health Impacts of E-Learning

Shruthi and Ashi (2021) identify adverse effects of prolonged e-learning, including eyesight problems, stress, anxiety, and vitamin D deficiency due to increased screen time and reduced physical activity. Effective training on maintaining physical health and managing stress is crucial for enhancing educators' performance in virtual environments.

Koreneva and Samilyk (2023) report on health issues from distance education, such as eye fatigue, visual impairment, and musculoskeletal disorders among educators. Their study emphasizes the need for a health-preserving culture, recommending educational materials on healthy practices, physical activity, and ergonomic guidance.

Employers play a critical role in ensuring the health and safety of online educators by implementing proactive measures, including ergonomic tools, mental health support, and work-life balance strategies. Such measures are essential for creating a supportive online teaching environment and addressing health challenges faced by remote educators.

Theoretical and Practical Frameworks for Online Education

Anderson (2008) notes that technological advancements in online education offer dynamic learning opportunities but also expose educators to risks related to intellectual property rights and compensation. In Georgia, existing copyright laws inadequately address

digital education concerns, such as unauthorized recordings of lectures. Universities often reuse recorded lectures without compensating educators, an issue not typically covered by standard teaching contracts.

To address these gaps, Georgia needs legislative reforms that recognize the unique aspects of online educational content. Specific regulations should be introduced to safeguard educators' intellectual property, ensuring fair compensation and control over their contributions. A proactive legal approach will enhance fairness and transparency in online education.

Addressing the Health and Labor Rights of Online Educators

The rise of digital technologies in academia has transformed labor dynamics, particularly for online educators. Global studies reveal that online educators often face additional responsibilities without adequate compensation or legal protections (Lupton, Mewburn, & Thomson, 2018). This challenge is evident in Georgia, where educators encounter similar issues.

International initiatives provide useful models for improving support for online educators in Georgia. Monash University's wellness strategies emphasize work-life balance and mental health support (Global Centre for Healthy Workplaces, n.d.). Incorporating such strategies could address the mental health and ergonomic challenges faced by Georgian online educators. Additionally, practical tools from the Kentucky Cabinet for Health and Family Services (2009) focus on mental health and nutrition, which could enhance workplace policies for online educators.

Advancements in ergonomics, such as dynamic lighting and ergonomic workspaces, offer crucial insights into improving remote working conditions (Salvendy, 2012). Combining these ergonomic advancements with wellness best practices highlights the need for comprehensive legal measures in Georgia to protect educators' physical and mental well-being.

Proactive Legal Solutions for Health and Safety

Proactive legal frameworks are essential to provide Georgian online educators with ergonomic tools and health resources. Germany's Workplaces Ordinance (2024) mandates ergonomic workstations and regular assessments, which could be adapted to improve conditions for Georgian remote educators. Implementing mandatory ergonomic assessments and subsidies for home office equipment could address physical health risks.

Mental health support is another critical area for legal reform. Australia's Work Health and Safety Act mandates mental health support and stress management (Safe Work Australia, 2023). Similar provisions in Georgia would ensure access to mental health services and effective workload management, crucial for preventing burnout.

Contract clauses addressing working conditions, overtime, and compensation are also vital. In the U.S., some institutions have introduced contract provisions for remote work, ensuring fair compensation and clear expectations (Ursinus College, 2024). Adopting similar

models in Georgia would protect educators from excessive workloads and ensure fair compensation for their labor.

IV. Safeguarding Educators' Rights in the Digital Classroom

Internationally, robust legal frameworks increasingly protect intellectual property rights for online educators. The U.S. Digital Millennium Copyright Act (DMCA) ensures that digital content creators, including educators, retain ownership of their materials (Michelson Institute for Intellectual Property, 2023). Georgia could benefit from similar legislation to safeguard educators' intellectual property, especially concerning the reuse of recorded lectures by universities without additional compensation.

Data privacy is another critical issue. The European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) sets a high standard for safeguarding personal data, requiring transparent and secure handling of personal information (Voigt & Von dem Bussche, 2017). Adopting similar data privacy standards in Georgia would protect educators from unauthorized use of their content and personal data, enhancing trust in the digital learning environment.

Effective dispute resolution mechanisms are essential for protecting educators' rights. Canada's employment standards offer a model for resolving workplace disputes and ensuring fair recourse for employees (Rights in the Workplace, 2022). Implementing similar mechanisms in Georgia would provide online educators with clear avenues to address contract violations, intellectual property disputes, and health-related issues, fostering a fairer and more secure working environment.

Proposed Reforms and Recommendations

To enhance the legal protection and support for online educators in Georgia, several targeted reforms are essential. Drawing inspiration from international practices, Georgia could benefit from implementing measures similar to Germany's Workplaces Ordinance by mandating ergonomic assessments and providing financial support for home office equipment. This approach would ensure that online educators work in health-conscious environments.

In addition to addressing physical health, mental health support is crucial. Emulating Australia's Work Health and Safety Act, Georgia should integrate counseling services, stress management programs, and workload management policies into its educational framework to combat burnout and promote well-being.

Intellectual property rights also require strengthening. Adopting comprehensive copyright laws akin to the U.S. Digital Millennium Copyright Act (DMCA) would protect educators' digital content and ensure fair compensation for its use. Similarly, incorporating data privacy standards similar to the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) would safeguard educators' personal data and online content, fostering a secure digital environment.

To complement these reforms, recommendations include clarifying contract terms to define intellectual property rights and compensation, providing ergonomic equipment, and establishing structured break

schedules to prevent physical strain. Furthermore, offering mental health resources and comprehensive training on health management and online teaching strategies would enhance educators' performance and resilience. Ensuring that medical insurance covers health issues related to working from home is also vital.

Together, these measures aim to create a supportive and equitable environment for online educators, addressing their needs comprehensively and improving the quality of online education in Georgia.

V. Conclusion

As online education evolves, Georgia faces pressing challenges that necessitate comprehensive legal reforms. Essential updates include enhancing intellectual property laws, improving ergonomic and health regulations, and providing robust mental health support for online educators. Clear and comprehensive contracts, ergonomic equipment, structured break schedules, and mental health resources are crucial to creating a fair and supportive environment.

By integrating global best practices and adapting them to local needs, Georgia can address the unique challenges faced by online educators, improving their well-being and the quality of education. Effective implementation of these reforms will align Georgia with international standards, fostering a positive and equitable work environment that supports educators and enhances the broader educational landscape.

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